

0.37 dS/m, 0.6% organic C, 0.06% total N, and 100 kg KMnO₄ oxidizable N/ha. Plots were 4 × 4 m with 3 replications of 6 treatments in a randomized block design. Jaya seedlings were transplanted at 35 d after seeding. Fields were treated with 10 ppm ZnSO₄ and 5.4 ppm P as single superphosphate. All urea sources except USG were surface mixed followed by flooding to 5 cm. USG was placed 10 cm deep between 4 hills.

Floodwater chemistry (pH, alkalinity, NH₄-N concentration) was monitored at 1330 h daily for 1 wk. Ammonia volatilization was studied separately on bare soil in pots. Semi-open can traps were calibrated in a pure ammonia system. Because the semi-open cans allow a fair exchange of air and water between the outside and the inside of the traps, an artificial microclimate does not develop inside the trap.

SCU did not affect grain yields, LCU decreased yield, and USG increased yield significantly (see table). LCU had no effect on dry matter, SCU and USG increased dry matter. USG significantly enhanced N uptake

Effect of slow-release urea fertilizers on yield and N uptake in a sodic soil. Haryana, India.

N source	Yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)			N uptake efficiency ^a (%)
	Grain	Straw	Total	Grain	Straw	Total	
No N	5.4	3.6	9.0	52	17	69	–
Prilled urea	7.4	5.9	13.2	76	29	105	28
Prilled urea split	7.4	6.2	13.6	84	31	115	35
SCU	7.3	7.4	14.6	86	48	134	50
LCU	6.6	6.4	13.1	71	36	107	29
USG ^b	8.8	8.3	17.1	96	49	145	59
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.5	0.3	0.8	12	11	22	18

^a Apparent N uptake efficiency = $\frac{\text{N uptake in treatment} - \text{N uptake in control}}{\text{N applied}} \times 100$. ^b 1-g granules.

by grains; both SCU and USG enhanced N uptake by straw. SCU and USG significantly increased total N uptake and improved apparent N uptake efficiency.

These results are consistent with floodwater chemistry and ammonia volatilization analyses. SCU and USG were most effective in maintaining low ammoniacal N concentration and alkalinity; PUW, PUS, and LCU were ineffective (see figure). SCU and USG reduced ammonia volatilization losses from prilled urea. Slow-release urea fertilizers like SCU and USG promise to improve fertilizer N efficiency in sodic soils. □

Dynamics of ammoniacal N in floodwater of a sodic soil following 120 kg N/ha applied as PUW or as PUS and slow-release and SCU and LCU. USG were deep placed at 10 cm.

Influence of organic amendments and oils on ammonia volatilization in flooded rice

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We measured NH₃ volatilization loss from urea with amendments and oils in flooded conditions in a greenhouse study. Soil was Beni silty clay loam, Aquic Hapludoll with 7.2 pH, 1.5% organic C, 24 meq/ 100 g of soil CEC, 24% free CaCO₃, and percolation rate of 14 mm/d. Pots were filled with 16 kg soil amended with 50 ppm of p-benzoquinone (PBQ) and catechol (Cate) and 50 g plant residue babul *Acacia arabica*, khair *Acacia catechue*, and inknut *Terminalia chebula*.

Jaya rice was transplanted at 23 d after seeding at 4 seedlings/ pot. At 5 d after transplanting, coated or uncoated urea was broadcast and incorporated and 1-g urea supergranules (USG) were deep placed 5 cm at the center of 4 hills. Treatments were replicated

twice. A cylindrical frame covered with a heavy-duty polythene bag was immediately placed on each pot and sealed. A petri dish filled with standard H₂SO₄ hung inside the frame. The petri dish was emptied every 4 d, the contents distilled for NH₃ by

N loss through NH₃ volatilization in flooded rice. Pantnagar (U.P.), India.

Treatment ^a loss	N loss (%)							Cumulative (%) in 28 d
	0-4 d	4-8 d	8-12 d	12-16 d	16-20 d	20-24 d	24-28 d	
Urea	4.2	4.4	4.7	2.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	18
USG deep placed	0.4	1.5	2.6	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	8
Linseed oil-coated urea	1.3	1.4	1.5	3.0	2.6	1.5	0.8	12
Neem oil-coated urea	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.9	2.6	1.5	0.8	12
Urea+p-benzoquinone	0.5	1.0	1.3	1.6	1.8	1.0	0.7	8
Urea + catechol	0.6	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.9	1.2	0.8	9
Urea + <i>Acacia arabica</i>	4.9	6.6	7.7	5.0	3.0	1.4	0.8	29
Urea + <i>Acacia catechol</i>	4.3	4.6	5.2	4.1	2.3	1.1	0.8	21
Urea + <i>Terminalia chebula</i>	4.4	5.7	6.2	4.8	3.0	1.1	0.8	26

^a Each treatment received 2.0 g urea.

microkjeldahl method, and ammonia volatilization estimated.
Ammonia volatilization losses in the

first 4 d after fertilizer application were highest with *Acacia arabica* and lowest with deep placed USG (see table).

Ammonia volatilization was higher with plant residues (more than 20%) than with urea. □

Effect of sowing time and planting method on rice yield per day

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A 3-yr study (1975-77) evaluated the effect of sowing time and method on rice (Ribe) productivity per day. Main plots were early, normal, and late sowing; subplots were planting methods, transplanting, broadcasting, and drilling. Subplots were 40 m².
In general, yield decreased with

Effect of sowing time and planting method on yield. Izmir, Turkey, 1975-77. ^a

Duration (d)	21 May		4 Jun		20 Jun			
	Yield		Yield		Yield			
	t/ha	kg/d	t/ha	kg/d	t/ha	kg/d		
127	5.1	40.2	140	<i>Transplanting</i> 5.6	40.0	130	5.1	39.2
120	4.5	37.5	117	<i>Drilling</i> 4.4	37.6	112	4.4	39.3
124	5.7	46.0	115	<i>Broadcasting</i> 5.7	49.6	111	5.1	45.9

^a Duration = day from sowing or transplanting to harvest. LSD at 5%: yield = 0.45, duration = 2.3, yield per day = 6.10.

delayed sowing (see table). Yields were higher with early season broadcasting

and lower with drilling in all sowing times. □

Efficacy of *Azospirillum brasilense* in increasing rice yield

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Azospirillum brasilense Tarrand et al. colonizes rice roots and fixes atmospheric N in soil. Its efficacy depends on the pre-inoculum soil N status. We studied the effect of *A. brasilense* in the field at different N (urea) application levels.

Peat-based *A. brasilense* inoculum mixed with well-powdered farmyard manure (2 kg inoculum + 15 kg farmyard manure/ ha) was uniformly

Grain and straw yield response to *A. brasilense* inoculation. Aduthurai, India.

Dose of nitrogenous fertilizer (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			% increase ^a	Straw yield (t/ha)		
	Without <i>A. brasilense</i>	With <i>A. brasilense</i>			Without <i>A. brasilense</i>	With <i>A. brasilense</i>	% increase ^a
0	3.1	3.1		0 ns	4.5	5.9	31*
25	3.5	3.8		9*	6.0	6.5	8 ns
50	4.1	4.4		7*	6.0	1.6	27*
75	3.6	4.4		22*	5.9	8.3	41*
100	4.3	4.1		ns	6.8	7.7	13*
CD (0.05)		0.2					

^a = significant difference, ns = not significant.

broadcast in the field after urea application. Roots of ADT36 seedlings were soaked in 1 kg *A. brasilense*/400 liters water solution for 20 min before transplanting.

Inoculation increased grain and straw yield over urea alone, particularly at 75 kg N/ha (see table). □

Phosphate sources for lowland rice

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We compared the efficiency of seven phosphate sources in a randomized block design replicated three times

during 1980 and 1981 wet seasons. The soil was clay loam (Typic Aquept) with pH 5.6, 0.65% organic C, and 9 kg Olsen's P/ha.

Phosphate sources were single superphosphate (6.9% P), Mussorie rock phosphate (9.5% P), mixture of single superphosphate and Mussorie rock phosphate at 3:1 and 1:1 P, urea ammonium phosphate (28-12-0 NPK), diammonium phosphate (18-20.6-0

NPK), and seedling root dip phosphate slurry prepared with single superphosphate, soil, water, and fresh cow dung at 1:2:3:1. We used 8.6 kg P/ha for the phosphate slurry and 17.8 kg P/ha for soil application. Pankaj was planted with 60-17.8-25 kg NPK/ha.

Single superphosphate and Mussorie rock phosphate at 1:1 gave better yields than 5 other treatments